

SYNTHESIS OF NEW LOCAL ANÆSTHETICS. PART II.

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In part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 13) some esters of α -acyloxy- β -aminoalkylisobutyric acid have been described which are endowed with local anæsthetic property. In the present investigation we have synthesised some compounds possessing the following general formula:

The starting material was α -hydroxy- β -chloroisobutyric acid described in Part I.

The α -hydroxy- β -chloroisobutyric acid was first esterified with various alcohols (ethyl, propyl, isopropyl and benzyl alcohols) and the resulting esters were heated with piperidine in dry benzene solution under pressure at 100°. The crude condensation products (unpurifiable liquids) were directly acylated with benzoyl chloride or *p*-nitrobenzoyl chloride. The hydrochloride of the acylated base (I) was purified and the products in the case of *p*-nitrobenzoyl derivatives were further reduced to the corresponding aminobenzoyl derivatives.

An alternative scheme was followed in which chloroacetone was condensed with piperidine to get piperidinoacetone previously described by Stoermer and Burkert (*Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 1200). It formed a bisulphite compound, which reacted with potassium cyanide solution to give β -piperidino- α -hydroxyisobutyronitrile (III). The hydrolysis of the nitrile with acids did not succeed as the substance decomposed into piperidine and the aliphatic component when the ester hydrochloride was treated with mildest of alkali.

The products described in the paper have strong local anaesthetic property, the toxicity and other details are being investigated at the King George Medical College, Lucknow. A full account of these will appear elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl α -Benzoyloxy- β -piperidinoisobutyrate.—Ethyl β -chloro- α -hydroxyisobutyrate (8 g., b.p. $85^{\circ}/11$ mm.) (*cf.* Fourneau "Organic Medicaments," 1925, p. 222) and piperidine (8.2 g.) was heated in benzene solution (50 c.c.) under pressure at 100° for 6 hours. After the removal of precipitated piperidine hydrochloride, the filtrate was washed with water, dried, solvent removed and the residue (5.5 g.) was directly heated with benzoyl chloride (5 g.) in toluene solution for 3 hours on an oil-bath. The cooled product was left at 0° for 12 hours. The separated solids were filtered and washed with dry ether and finally crystallised from hot acetone in needles, m.p. 128° . (Found: N, 3.95; Cl, 10.28. $C_{18}H_{26}O_4NCl$ requires N, 3.94; Cl, 9.98 per cent.)

Hydrochloride of Ethyl α -p-Nitrobenzoyloxy- β -piperidinoisobutyrate.—(I, R = Et, R' = $C_6H_4NO_2$).—A mixture of *o*-nitrobenzoyl chloride (9 g.), ethyl α -hydroxy- β -piperidinoisobutyrate (8.6 g.) and toluene (100 c.c.) was heated on the oil-bath for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The product was isolated as described before. The *hydrochloride* crystallised from acetone—alcohol or from hot acetone in needles, m.p. 76° , yield 14.7 g. The substance crystallised with a molecule of acetone. (Found: N, 6.21; Cl, 7.4. $C_{18}H_{25}O_6N_2Cl$, C_3H_6O requires N, 6.1; Cl, 7.7 per cent). The substance on heating gives off acetone which was qualitatively tested and established. [Found (in the material dried in high vacuo at 68°): N, 6.75; Cl, 8.5. $C_{18}H_{25}O_6N_2Cl$ requires N, 6.9; Cl, 8.8 per cent).]

Ethyl α -p-Aminobenzoyloxy- β -piperidinoisobutyrate.—The foregoing nitro ester hydrochloride (5 g.) was catalytically reduced in alcohol with platinum oxide and hydrogen. The solution after reduction was filtered and three-fourths of this solvent removed in *vacuo*. The residue was left in *vacuo*. After three days, crystallisation was complete. The product was washed with dry ether. It could not be satisfactorily recrystallised as considerable loss of material occurs, m.p. 102° . (Found: Cl, 9.1. $C_{18}H_{27}O_4N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 9.5 per cent.)

Propyl α -Benzoyloxy- β -piperidinoisobutyrate.—The acid (15 g.) was esterified with propyl alcohol in the usual manner, b.p. $120^{\circ}/15$ mm. (Found: Cl, 19.49. $C_7H_{13}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 19.6 per cent). A mixture of

the foregoing ester (9.8 g.), piperidine (10 g.) in benzene was heated under pressure as described before. The crude product was benzoylated by heating with benzoyl chloride in toluene solution. The *hydrochloride* (I, R=C₃H₇, R' = Ph) was crystallised from acetone-ether mixture, m.p. 115°. (Found : Cl, 9.8. C₁₉H₂₈O₄NCl requires Cl, 9.6 per cent).

The preparation of (I, R = *iso* C₃H₇, H in place of R'CO).—*iso*Propyl β-chloro-α-hydroxyisobutyrate (*cf.* Part I) (9.3 g.), piperidine (9 g.) in dry benzene (5 c.c.) was heated at 100° under pressure for 6 hours. The precipitated piperidine hydrochloride was removed and the benzene solution well washed with water, dried and the solvent removed. The residual oil in ether was converted into the hydrochloride by ethereal hydrogen chloride and the precipitated solids were crystallised from a mixture of ether and alcohol, m.p. 115°. (Found : Cl, 13.6. C₁₂H₂₄O₃NCl requires Cl, 13.4 per cent).

Hydrochloride of isoPropyl α-Benzoyloxy-β-piperidinoisobutyrate (I, R' = Ph, R = *iso*-C₃H₇) was converted into the free ester (2 g.) and was heated with benzoyl chloride (1.5 g.) at 130° for 1 hour. After cooling the reaction mixture was kept in contact with dry ether at 0° for 12 hours. The solids were collected and crystallised from a mixture of hot acetone and ether, m.p. 156°. (Found : Cl, 9.32. C₁₉H₂₈O₄NCl requires Cl, 9.6 per cent).

Hydrochloride of isoPropyl p-Nitrobenzoyloxy-β-piperidinoisobutyrate.—*p*-Nitrobenzoyl chloride (5 g.) in dry toluene (50 c.c.) was heated with *iso*-propyl α-hydroxy-β-piperidino isobutyrate (5.1 g.). The product, isolated as described before, was crystallised from a mixture of acetone and alcohol in needles, m.p. 61°. (Found : N, 6.54; Cl, 8.30. C₁₉H₂₇O₆N₂Cl requires N, 6.76; Cl, 8.56 per cent).

The foregoing nitro compound was reduced with platinum oxide catalyst as described before but the product could not be satisfactorily recrystallised as it was extremely hygroscopic.

Hydrochloride of Benzyl α-Benzoyloxy-β-piperidinoisobutyrate.—Benzyl β-chloro-α-hydroxyisobutyrate (*cf.* Part I) (7 g.) and piperidine (5.5 g.) was condensed and the product isolated in the usual manner. The crude product (1 g.) and benzoyl chloride (0.7 g.) were heated at 150° for 2-3 hours. The semi-solid mass obtained after the addition of ether, solidified on keeping at 0° for 2 weeks. It was recrystallised from a mixture of ether and alcohol, m.p. 195-97°. (Found : Cl, 8.7. C₂₃H₃₈O₄NCl requires Cl, 8.5 per cent).

Piperidinoacetone was prepared by the method of Stoermer and Burkert (*loc. cit.*). (Oxime, m.p. 104°; phenylhydrazone, m.p. 63°).

β-Piperidino-*α*-hydroxyisobutyronitrile.—Piperidinoacetone (13 g.) was shaken with a solution of sodium hydrogen sulphite (18 g. in 18 c.c. of water) in the cold. A solution of potassium cyanide (10 g. in 10 c.c. of water) was added with shaking, the temperature was not allowed to exceed 5°. The separated oil was extracted with ether and then the solvent removed, yield 6.5 g. It decomposes on distillation under reduced pressure. The foregoing nitrile was hydrolysed to the ester in absolute alcoholic solution with hydrogen chloride by boiling for 1½ hours. On treatment with sodium carbonate solution the ester hydrochloride decomposed into piperidine and ethyl *αβ*-dihydroxyisobutyrate.

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INDIGOID VAT DYES OF THE ISATIN SERIES. PART II. 3-INDOLE-2'-(6'-METHYL)-THIONAPHTHENEINDIGOS.

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It has been found from a study of the tinctorial properties of 2-(5-methyl) thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 679) and those of the corresponding 2-(6-methyl) derivatives (Guha, *ibid.*, 1936, 13, 94) that Martinet's rule (*Rev. Gen. Mat. Col.*, 1921, 28, 17) is applicable to 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene indigos (Bezdik and Friedlander, *Monatsh*, 1908, 29, 386; E. P. 344/08; G. P. 226244; Mayer and Schönfelder, *Ber.*, 1922, 85, 2972; G. P. 213504; E. P. 20003/08; Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 423) as far as one methyl group in the thionaphthene part of the molecule is concerned. Further, Guha and Basu-Mallik prepared 3-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphthene indigos (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 395) and showed that these indigoid dyes impart deeper shades on cotton and on wool than those of the 2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthyleneindigos (Guha, *loc. cit.*).

In view of these observations, the present work was undertaken with the object of preparing 3-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigos and comparing them with those of the corresponding 5'-methyl derivatives (Guha and Basu-Mallik, *loc. cit.*). It was also intended to examine how far Martinet's rule is obeyed by 3-indole-2'-thionaphthene indigo, commercially known as Thioindigo Scarlet R (Bezdzik and Friedlander, *Monatsh.*, 1908, 28, 376; E. P. 17162/06; G. P. 241327) and its derivatives (Ciba Red G, etc., E. P. 19158/07 and G. P. 277358) having one methyl group present in the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule.

6-Methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Friedlander, 9, 589; Auwers and Thies, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 2293) has, therefore, been condensed with isatin, 5-chloro-, 5-bromo-, 5:7-dibromo-, 5-bromo-7-nitro-, and 5:7-dinitroisatin and the corresponding vat dyes obtained easily. All of them when rubbed develop a beautiful lustre, although not coppery like ordinary indigo. This property is also exhibited by the corresponding 5'-methyl derivatives (Guha and Basu-Mallik, *loc. cit.*) now studied by the present author for comparison. They resemble the corresponding 5'-methyl derivatives in solubility, in the action of heat above 310° and in the action of cold concentrated sulphuric acid in producing characteristic colouration. Most of these dyes possess well-developed dyeing properties. All of them dye wool from an acid bath producing uniformly and fully developed shades. They dissolve in alkaline hydrosulphite giving vats, the colours of which are similar to those of the corresponding 5'-methyl compounds, and from these vats the original dyes are reprecipitated on oxidation. The colours imparted on cotton by the mother compound, its chloro, and bromo derivatives are slightly lighter than those of the shades of the original substances but in case of dibromo, bromonitro, and dinitro derivatives uniform deep shades have been obtained.

These 3-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigos are decisively much lighter in colour than the analogously composed 5'-methyl derivatives (Guha and Basu-Mallik, *loc. cit.*), a result in conformity with Martinet's rule. It has also been found that the 6'-methyl dyes obtained from isatin, 5-chloro-, and its 5-bromo derivatives developed colours on cotton and on wool which are deeper than those of the nearly corresponding 6-methyl-compounds in the acenaphthenequinone series [*cf.*, 2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthyleneindigos and 3-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigos, Guha and Guha and Basu-Mailik, *loc. cit.*].

The colours obtained from the dyes mentioned in this paper and

those from the corresponding 5'-methyl derivatives (Guha and Basu-Mallik, *loc. cit.*), are compared in the following table.

Substances.	Colour on wool.	Colour on cotton.
3-Indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphthene-indigo	Red	Light red
3-Indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphthene-indigo	Brilliant scarlet red	Light red
3-(5-Chloro)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Red	Red
3-(5-Chloro)-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Scarlet red	Scarlet red
3-(5-Bromo)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Red	Red
3-(5-Bromo)-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Scarlet red	Scarlet red
3-(5 : 7-Dibromo)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Light scarlet red	Scarlet red
3-(5 : 7-Dibromo)-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Deep red	Deep red
3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Red	Dark red
3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro)-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Dark red	Dark red
3-(5 : 7-Dinitro)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Blood red	Dark red.
3-(5 : 7-Dinitro)-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.	Dark red	Dark red

Further work for studying the preparation and properties of 3-indole-2'-(4'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigos has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The indigoid dyes have been prepared by a method similar to that described by Guha and Basu-Mullik (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of 3-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigos.

3-Indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.

It was prepared from isatin (0.735 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.82 g.) in 60 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. It separated in silky scarlet bundles of sharp needles. The product (1.194 g.) crystallised from glacial acetic acid in silky red crystals. It is moderately soluble in benzene, acetone and chloroform. It dyes wool in red shades from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat. (Found : S, 11.33. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2NS$ requires S, 10.92 per cent).

3-(5-Chloro)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo separated as long red needles by the condensation of 5-chloroisatin (0.544 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 115 c.c. of acetic acid and 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The dye (0.864 g.) crystallised from pyridine in clusters of deep red needles. It dyes both wool and cotton in red shades. (Found : Cl, 10.85. $C_{17}H_{10}O_2NClS$ requires Cl, 10.83 per cent).

3-(5-Bromo)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo was obtained as long silky red needles by reacting 5-bromoisatin (0.452 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in 75 c.c. of acetic acid and 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The substance (0.652 g.) was crystallised from pyridine in fibre-like deep red long needles when it lost its silky lustre. The dyeing shades on wool and on cotton are similar to those of the chloro compound but is slightly deeper in each case. (Found : Br, 21.13. $C_{17}H_{10}O_2NBrS$ requires Br, 21.51 per cent).

3-(5:7-Dibromo)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo separated from 5:7-dibromoisatin (0.61 g.) and the methylhydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in 100 c.c. of acetic acid and 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid in deep red fibre-like small needles. The dye (0.819 g.) crystallised from nitrobenzene in beautiful foliated needles. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with an olive-brown colour. It dyes wool in light scarlet-red shades and cotton in scarlet-red shades. (Found : Br, 35.39. $C_{17}H_9O_2NBr_2S$ requires Br, 35.47 per cent).

3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo was prepared from 5-bromo-7-nitroisatin (0.813 g.) and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in 95 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and 6 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The light scarlet-red substance (1.099 g.) separated from pyridine in fine hair-like needles. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a yellowish-green colour. It dyes wool in red shades and cotton in dark red shades. (Found : Br, 19.43. $C_{17}H_9O_4N_2BrS$ requires Br, 19.18 per cent).

3-(5:7-Dinitro)-indole-2'-(6'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.—The dark red crystalline precipitate (0.692 g.), obtained from 6:7-dinitroisatin (0.474 g.)

and 6-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in 65 c.c. of acetic acid and 3—4 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid, separated from pyridine in fine needles. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with an olive-brown colouration. It dyes wool in blood-red shades and cotton in dark red shades. (Found: S, 8.45. $C_{17}H_9O_2N_2S$ requires S, 8.35 per cent).

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